

SiO_xN_y thin films with variable refraction index: Microstructural, chemical and mechanical properties

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Abstract

In this work amorphous silicon oxynitride films with similar composition (ca. Si_{0.40}N_{0.45}O_{0.10}) were deposited by reactive magnetron sputtering from a pure Si target under different N₂–Ar mixtures. Rutherford backscattering (RBS) studies revealed that the coatings presented similar composition but different density. The mechanical properties evaluated by nanoindentation show also a dependence on the deposition conditions that does not correlate with a change in composition. An increase in nitrogen content in the gas phase results in a decrease of hardness and Young's modulus.

The microstructural study by high resolution scanning electron microscopy (SEM-FEG) on non-metalized samples allowed the detection of a close porosity in the form of nano-voids (3–15 nm in size), particularly in the coatings prepared under pure N₂ gas. It has been shown how the presence of the close porosity allows tuning the refraction index of the films in a wide range of values without modifying significantly the chemical, thermal and mechanical stability of the film.

1. Introduction

In past years, silicon oxynitride films have been the subject of great interest not only for their excellent properties such as chemical inertness, high thermal stability and corrosion resistance, but also their combination of adequate mechanical, optical and electrical properties [1–5].

Silicon oxynitride is transparent in the visible range and the refraction index can be varied from that of pure silicon dioxide (1.47) to the one of pure silicon nitride (2.3). A continuous change in its composition [2,6] allows to obtain films with different optical, electrical and also mechanical properties [7]. The possibility of tuning these properties is important for many industrial applications such as passivation and masking layers in microelectronics, solar cells, luminescent devices [8,9] or antireflection coatings [10,11].

Navid and Pilon [12] studied theoretically the possibility of tuning the optical properties of thin films of similar composition introducing nano-pores with different shape, size and spatial distribution. The introduction of pores decreases the refraction index of the coatings. Nanoporous thin films have been studied exten-

sively in recent years [13–16] due to potential applications such as catalysts, sensors, thermal barriers and optical devices like waveguides, reflectors or filters [17,18]. Also some work has been done in controlling the porosity of thin films by changing the deposition conditions as substrate temperature and gas mixture in plasma enhanced CVD [19]. In the present work the sputtering technology is used to prepare silicon oxynitride films with tailored porosity and refraction index by controlling the N₂ and Ar gas mixture, while keeping sputtering power, deposition time and distance to target constant. In addition, and according to our knowledge, most of the previous papers are related to the introduction of open porosity and no work was previously reported to control the formation of close nanoporosity in this type of silicon oxynitride coatings. The method presented here is simple and can easily be up-scaled.

The aim of this work is to establish a correlation between the deposition conditions, morphology, mechanical and optical properties of silicon oxynitride thin films. A tailored control of the refraction index will be presented without modifying significantly the chemical, thermal and mechanical stability of the films.

2. Experimental

Silicon oxynitride coatings were deposited on Si (1 0 0), glass and AISI M2 substrates by reactive magnetron sputtering from

Fig. 1. RBS experimental results and SIMNRA simulations for samples prepared with 20, 50 and 100% N_2 .

a pure Si target (Kurt J. Lesker 99.999%), using an RF sputtering source at a power of 150 W and a distance target-substrate of 10 cm.

Before deposition, the base pressure was 1×10^{-4} Pa. Mixtures of argon and nitrogen were used as sputtering gases, the fraction of $N_2/(N_2 + Ar)$ was varied from 0 to 100% (20, 50, 100%), while the total pressure was kept constant at 1.33 Pa and a deposition time of 3 h.

The thickness and morphology of the samples were studied by scanning electron microscopy (HITACHI S-4800 SEM-FEG). The samples were cleaved from coatings grown onto silicon, and were observed without metallization in cross-sectional views at 1–2 kV. Thickness was also evaluated using a Mahr mechanical profilometer.

The composition and the atomic density of the films were determined by Rutherford backscattering spectrometry (RBS) using the 3 MV tandem accelerator of the National Centre for Accelerators in Sevilla (Spain). The spectra were measured with a 2 MeV He^+ beam and the detection angle was 165° . The experimental spectra were analysed using the SIMNRA simulation code [20]. The composition of the coatings was also evaluated by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. A Leybolb Heraeus LH10 Spectrometer was used, working in the constant analyser energy mode with a pass-energy of 50 eV. The binding energy reference was taken as the main component of the C 1s peak at 284.6 eV for adventitious carbon. For quantification the XPS spectra were subjected to background subtraction (Shirley background) and sensitivity factors supplied by the instrument manufacturer were used.

The mechanical properties of the samples were obtained by nanoindentation, using a Hysitron Inc. Triboindenter with a Berkovich tip at a maximum load of 1000 μN .

Optical characterization was performed on films deposited on glass substrates, using a Fourier transform visible–infrared spectrophotometer (Bruker IFS-66) attached to a microscope, operating in reflection mode. A $4\times$ objective with a numerical aperture of 0.1 (light cone of $\pm 5.7^\circ$) was used to irradiate the sample and collect the reflected light at quasi-normal incidence. The refraction index of the silicon oxynitride coatings was determined by fitting the optical specular reflectance using spectra generated by a Mathematica code based on scalar wave approximation, as described elsewhere [21].

The layer thickness and optical constants were confirmed by spectroscopic ellipsometry measurements. These measurements were performed with a variable angle spectroscopic ellipsometer (VASE) manufactured by the J.A. Woollam Co. The measurements were executed with three angles of incidence ($65\text{--}70\text{--}75^\circ$) and a wavelength range of 300–1700 nm in 10 nm steps. The data were analysed using the WVASE32 software version 3.441 developed by the J.A. Woollam Co.

Cross-section and planar view samples were analysed by electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) coupled to a TEM microscope (Philips CM200). “In situ” heating up to 900 $^\circ C$ was also carried out in this equipment.

3. Results and discussion

Fig. 1 shows the RBS results and SIMNRA simulations for the SiO_xN_y samples prepared with different N_2 fraction in the gas phase. The atomic densities, as determined from the RBS analysis and compositions by RBS and XPS are given in Table 1. Although the N signal, at channel 135, is distorted due to electronic noise, the O peak is clearly visible, starting in channel 160, from which we can know the oxygen content of the samples. Moreover, from the fitting of the Si signal it is possible to determine (via stopping power) the global amount of O + N within the films.

The analysis performed in both cases showed similar concentrations of Si, N, O and small amounts of superficial carbon contamination independently of the N_2 fraction in the gas phase. Although there was no introduction of oxygen as sputtering gas, the higher reactivity of silicon with oxygen than with nitrogen makes very difficult to exclude the oxygen contamination of this type of coatings, as previously shown by other authors [22,23]. In case of our samples, the presence of oxygen is due to unavoidable contamination probably caused by any or a combination of the following reasons: (a) a certain residual oxygen pressure remaining in the deposition chamber before deposition (maximum value the residual vacuum of the chamber 1×10^{-4} Pa) and (b) oxygen desorption from target, substrate and chamber walls; a slight decrease in oxygen contamination seems to be achieved when a higher amount of argon is used.

It would be expected that changing the N_2 fraction in the gas phase would produce coatings with different nitrogen concentrations. The similar composition of the SiN_xO_y samples for such a wide range of gas mixture has been previously observed by other authors [23,24]. Particularly Vila et al. [23], presents RBS experiments showing N/Si ratios ranging from 1.30 to 1.37 for four different SiN_x coatings prepared from a Si target by reactive sputtering using mixtures of Ar and N_2 , with $N_2\%$ in the gas mixture of 50, 70, 85 and 100%. These values are similar to ours (1.15, 1.38 and 1.28 for 20, 50 and 100% N_2) and present even less variation in their compositions. The compositional data determined by RBS and presented here have been complemented with XPS (X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy) analysis in selected samples (see Table 1). Although this is a more surface sensitive technique, similar composition was found for the three samples. The higher content in oxygen in this case (when compared with RBS) is due to additional surface oxidation.

Table 1
Thickness (from SEM and mechanical profilometry), atomic density (from RBS), chemical composition (from RBS and XPS), Auger parameter (from XPS) and mechanical properties (from nanoindentation) of the SiO_xN_y coatings.

Sample	% N ₂	Thickness (nm)		Areal density (at.%/cm ²)	Chemical composition (at. %)								Auger parameter ^a		Mechanical properties (GPa)	
		SEM	Profilometry		RBS			XPS				ε ₁ (eV)	ε ₂ (eV)	H	Er	
					Si	N	O	Si	N	O	C					
S1	20	1100	1058	80×10^{17}	41	47	12	39	33	24	4	1713.6	1713.8	13.6	159.3	
S2	50	426	440	37×10^{17}	34	47	19	38	33	23	6	1713.8	1713.8	14.1	149.4	
S3	100	395	420	28×10^{17}	35	45	20	37	32	26	5	1713.9	1713.8	9.0	112.9	

^a Auger parameter of Si: binding energy of Si2p photoelectron peak plus kinetic energy of Si KLL Auger peak. Data for samples before (a1) and after (a2) Ar⁺ bombardment for surface cleaning.

Previous results by Yao et al. [22] report XPS N/Si ratios similar to ours for 20, 40 and 75% N₂, as an example, for the sample prepared at 20% N₂ the reported oxygen amount on the coating is 16.7 at.%. We have also evaluated the Auger parameter of Si before (a₁) and after bombardment (a₂) to clean the surface from adventitious contaminations. The obtained values (in Table 1) are very similar for all coatings and characteristic of silicon oxynitride, proving the nature of these films. The reproducibility of oxygen incorporation in these films have been therefore proved in our system and also in the works from Yao and Vila [22,23].

In order to determine the possible post-deposition contamination in these films electron energy loss spectroscopy of cross-sectional TEM samples was also performed. Fig. 2 presents the EELS spectra from an area of around 150 nm in diameter in the middle of the cross-section of sample S3. The silicon ionization edge is typical of a silicon oxynitride [25]. O and N *k*-edge have been also recorded.

The thickness of the films, as determined by SEM and profilometry, are also included in Table 1. This parameter decreases with the % N₂ in the sputtering atmosphere. This means that the sputtering rates and growth mechanisms of the film are dependent on the atmosphere (% N₂). In fact, our deposition rates decrease from 10 to 2 nm/min when N₂% is increased from 0 to 100%, matching well with the deposition rate curve established by Yao et al. [24]. Our N₂% variation in the gas mixture (from 20 to 100) corresponds approximately to the SiN_x reactive mode region in Yao's curve. In this region, deposition rates are practically constant between 50 and 100 N₂% which also favours similar composition values. It seems therefore, that our working conditions lead to target poisoning through the formation of a SiO_xN_y compound onto the target. Other authors have reached the same conclusions [24,26].

Fig. 2. EELS spectra: *L*_{2,3} ionization edge of silicon and *K* ionization edges of nitrogen and oxygen of cross-section of sample S3.

Since the coatings present similar composition, the areal density determined by RBS may be directly proportional to the thickness. In our case for sample prepared with 100% N₂ in the gas phase, the obtained areal density value is around 19% less than expected according to thickness values in Table 1. It is therefore expected that the mass density of the films decreases with an increase in N₂% in the gas phase during deposition. As it will be shown below the presence of a nano-porosity is the origin of such mass density changes as shown by high resolution microstructural analysis.

The evaluation of the mechanical properties of these samples by nanoindentation shows that the hardness (*H*) and elastic modulus (*E_r*) varies from *H* = 9.0 GPa and *E_r* = 112.9 GPa for sample prepared under pure N₂ to *H* = 13.6 GPa and *E_r* = 159.3 GPa for the samples prepared under 20% of N₂ (see Table 1). Fig. 3 shows typical load–depth curves. The indentation depth is larger for samples prepared with high N₂% at identical maximum load. The coating density is also affecting the mechanical response. Microstructural changes may explain the mechanical behavior changes, since the chemical composition of the coatings is the same.

Fig. 4 shows SEM-FEG cross-sectional views of the films grown under different N₂ fraction. The pictures show a columnar like growth of the films. At low N₂% these columns are fine, compact and clearly distinguishable. An increase in the nitrogen fraction (50% N₂) during deposition results in coarse columns. The columnar structure is typical of coatings grown under low energetic ion bombardment and limited adatom mobility [27]. It is also possible to see the voids between the columns, characteristic of zone 1 in Thornton's model [27].

At 100% N₂ the columnar structure almost vanishes but instead nano-pores can clearly be seen in the cross-section. Fig. 5 shows a view at larger magnification of this sample where a close porosity formed by nano-voids in the size range 3–15 nm in diameter is

Fig. 3. Load–depth curves for the samples deposited under different N₂ fraction.

Fig. 4. SEM-FEG micrographs for samples prepared under 20, 50 and 100% N₂.

clearly visible. The Raman spectroscopy analysis of this sample [28] shows the presence of an intense and narrow band at 2330 cm⁻¹ assigned to molecular nitrogen that should be trapped inside the nanopores. This band disappears for samples for which nano-voids are not visible in the SEM-FEG images. In fact at low argon pressures a transition zone has been described [26] where densely packed fibrous grains were identified. Our work shows that under these growing conditions nitrogen is likely to be trapped inside the nano-voids. In the case of columnar growth gas may diffuse through voids between columns.

In a paper, Criado et al. [1] also proposed the presence of voids in silicon oxynitride coatings deposited by PECVD as a function of the deposition conditions and thermal treatments. However, no microscopic evidence or information regarding shape and type (open or close) of porosity was given there.

Therefore the differences in density and mechanical properties can be mainly attributed to the different morphology of the coatings and less to the compositional changes. The reduction of hardness and plasticity presented is attributed to the higher porosity of the coatings prepared at 100% N₂. A review about the influence of porosity on the Young's Modulus can be found in the literature [29].

Fig. 5. SEM-FEG micrographs for sample prepared under 100% N₂.

The refraction index of the coatings was measured by vis-IR spectroscopy and the spectra were simulated using the scalar wave approximation [21,27]. For simulation the spectra were taken in the range 450–1200 nm and the refraction index is given by the best fit in all range. The refraction indexes obtained through simulations were 1.86, 1.73 and 1.60, respectively for samples prepared with 20, 50 and 100% N₂ in the gas phase. As expected the refraction indexes are between the refraction indexes of SiO₂ (1.47) and Si₃N₄ (2.3) and are consistent (according to calculated data in [12]) with expected values for different porosities in the films. In addition, these values follow the same tendency as hardness and reduced Young's Modulus: the increase in the N₂ ratio in the gas phase produces a decrease of refraction index and mechanical properties (*H* and *E_r*) as expected from the increase of close nano-porosity in the films. Thickness values, although also consistent with data obtained by SEM and profilometry, are affected by a larger error for the thinnest films where only one oscillation is present. At that point also an ellipsometry analysis was undertaken to have alternative values on refraction index and thicknesses of the films.

The refraction index of the samples, as determined by ellipsometry, decreases with the increase of the wavelength. For comparison with vis-IR results, Table 2 shows the refraction index of the samples obtained at 550 nm by ellipsometry. These values are in good agreement with the results obtained by vis-IR spectrometry and profilometry.

Effective medium approximations can be used to model effective properties of heterogeneous media. Navid and Pilon in their work [12] expresses the effective relative electrical permittivity of a heterogeneous media ($\epsilon_{r,eff}$) according to Maxwell-Garnett theory, as a function of the dielectric constants of the continuous ($\epsilon_{r,c}$) and dispersed phase ($\epsilon_{r,d}$) and the volume fraction occupied by the dispersed phase (ϕ):

$$\epsilon_{r,eff} = \epsilon_r e^{1 - \frac{3\phi(\epsilon_{r,c} - \epsilon_{r,d})}{2\epsilon_{r,c} + \epsilon_{r,d} + \phi(\epsilon_{r,c} - \epsilon_{r,d})}} \quad (1)$$

Assuming similar composition of the films and taking the refraction indexes obtained by ellipsometry at 550 nm the volume

Table 2
Refraction index at 550 nm wavelength and thickness as determined by ellipsometry for the SiO_xN_y coatings.

% N ₂	<i>n</i>	Thickness (nm)
20	1.76	1160
50	1.68	524
100	1.60	424

Fig. 6. EELS spectra: $L_{2,3}$ ionization edge of silicon and K ionization edges of nitrogen and oxygen of sample prepared under 100% N_2 at room temperature and at 900 °C.

fraction occupied by the nano-porosity (dispersed phase) can be calculated. For the calculations the dielectric constant of sample prepared with 20% N_2 was taken as the dielectric function of the continuous phase. Since the nano-voids are filled with molecular N_2 trapped during deposition (having a pressure of 1.33 Pa), the dielectric constant has been considered equal to 1 (the same as vacuum). The calculated volume fraction occupied by the pores resulted in 20% for the sample S3 and 1% for sample S2 as compared to sample S1.

The most interesting behavior of the coatings is therefore the presence of closed nano-porosity in comparison to the more usual open porosity features. The coatings have variable refraction index and at the same time they keep their mechanical resistance (variation in hardness and Young's modulus is moderate). It is expected that the reduction of open porosity will limit the accessibility of corrosive gases and the actual surface area for gas interaction would be very low, especially for sample prepared with 100% nitrogen in the gas phase.

The thermal stability of these samples in vacuum was investigated by EELS experiments, performed inside a TEM. For this study planar view samples were prepared. The samples were heated in situ up to 900 °C and the spectra were registered at different temperatures. Fig. 6 shows the $Si L_{2,3}$ ionization edge and the K edges of N and O of the sample presenting the nano-voids, at room temperature and after heating at 900 °C.

The silicon ionization edge is as expected typical of a silicon oxynitride [25], and no changes in shape of the edges occurred until 900 °C, indicating that the presence of the nano-voids does not affect the thermal stability of the sample and no compositional changes occurred during heat treatment. It has been also observed by SEM that the nano-voids are stable at least up to 900 °C during sample heating.

4. Conclusions

In this work the effects of deposition gas mixture (N_2 -Ar) on the composition, structure and properties of SiO_xN_y thin films were studied. By changing the N_2 -Ar ratio it is possible to deposit films of similar composition with different structure and thickness as it can be seen from the RBS, SEM and profilometry results.

Although similar properties would be expected from similar compositions, the film structure influences its mechanical and opti-

cal properties. The decrease of hardness and Young's Modulus with the increase of N_2 fraction can be correlated with the presence of porosity for the films prepared under high $N_2\%$.

The films present refraction indexes between the refraction index of silicon dioxide ($n SiO_2 = 1.47$) and silicon nitride ($n Si_3N_4 = 2.3$) and it can be controlled mainly by the microstructure of the films without major changes in the composition of the films. The difference of refraction index is therefore associated mainly to a difference in porosity. In this sense, it is possible to tune the optical properties of silicon oxynitride films regarding the possible applications.

The porosity of the films is constituted by spherical nano-voids with a diameter range of 3–15 nm. The formation of closed porosity is favoured by depositions in pure nitrogen by the low energetic ion bombardment and limited adatom mobility when compared with argon atmospheres.

It has been shown how the presence of the closed porosity allows tuning the refraction index of the films in a wide range of values (1.86–1.60) without major modification of the chemical composition. Thermal stability of the films after heat treatment up to 900 °C in vacuum has been also demonstrated.

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